

TOPONYMIC CLASSIFICATIONS

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ANNOTATION

Toponymy can be studied geographically as well as linguistically according to its features of geographical and linguistic. The article illustrates the principles of toponyms as well as it includes some methods of descriptive and semantic analysis of toponyms. Moreover, it is given various types of toponyms and features of them.

KEY WORDS: toponym, toponymic conceptual semantics, verbalizers, geographical source, psychological source, toponym types

Toponymy is the study of place names, their origins, meanings, usage, and importance in a geographical context. It is a branch of linguistics and geography that focuses on the etymology, history, and cultural significance of names given to geographical locations, including cities, towns, villages, rivers, mountains, and other landmarks.

The field of toponymy examines the various factors that contribute to the naming of places. This can include linguistic aspects, historical events, cultural influences, mythology, geographical features, political changes, and the individuals or groups responsible for assigning names to these locations.

Toponymy involves the analysis of place names from different perspectives:

Etymology: Studying the linguistic roots and origins of names, including their historical development, linguistic elements, and changes in pronunciation or spelling over time.

Cultural Significance: Understanding the cultural, historical, or social relevance of place names within specific communities or regions. Place names often reflect the traditions, beliefs, or historical events associated with a particular area.

Geographical Context: Exploring the relationship between place names and the physical features or characteristics of the landscape. Names often describe or refer to geographical landmarks such as mountains, rivers, forests, or other natural elements.

Mapping and Cartography: Integrating place names into maps and geographical representations to accurately identify and locate different regions, cities, or landmarks.

Standardization and Preservation: Developing systems for standardizing place names and preserving their cultural and linguistic heritage, especially in multilingual or multicultural regions.

Understanding toponymy provides insights into the cultural, historical, and linguistic aspects of a region or country. It helps in preserving cultural heritage, studying the evolution of languages, understanding historical events, and facilitating effective communication in geographical contexts. Toponymy is an interdisciplinary field that intersects linguistics, history, geography, anthropology, and cultural studies.

Toponyms are one of the main linguistic and cultural-spiritual wealth of all the nations which they have their own history of the toponyms which was created over many centuries. Toponyms reflect the unique observations, experiences, worldviews and various beliefs of the people from the ancient times to the present day. Toponymy is the study of “*toponyms*” that are proper names of places, also known as “*place name*” or “*geographic name*”, their origins and meanings, use and typology. In a more specific sense, the term “*toponymy*” refers to an inventory of toponyms, while the discipline researching such names is referred to as “*toponymics*” or “*toponomastics*”. Toponymy is a branch of onomastics which is the study of proper names of all kinds. Toponym is the general term for a proper name of any geographical feature, and full scope of the term also includes proper names of all cosmographical features. According to the *Oxford English Dictionary*, the word “toponymy” first appeared in English in 1876. Since then, the word “toponym” has come to replace the term “place-name” in professional discourse among geographers. Furthermore, according to Merriam Webster Dictionary toponymy is the place-names of a region or language or especially the etymological study of them.

At the moment a name is given to an object, the language of the name-giver provides both the elements needed and the structure to join them together. The elements consist of semantic and morphologic units – units of meaning and form - called *words* and *morphemes*. The former are the smallest units that may occur independently, the latter the even smaller particles, like suffixes and affixes forming part of or joined to them. The structure is provided that in the form of a set of rules called *grammar*, that defines the way the language can be used to

convey (*communicate*) meaning. An important constituent of grammar is the *syntax*, determining the way words should be linked together into larger semantic conglomerates. Most names start their existence as such a semantic conglomerate.

A mixture of lexical, grammatical and semantic principles is considered as the disadvantage rather than the advantage of such classifications. The scientific approach assumes that the set is divided into subsets as many times as many principles of division there are, meanwhile the divided subset can also be subdivided. It is obvious that it is impossible to create a unified classification of place names, which would reflect the entire multidimensional nature of the toponymic vocabulary. Classifying toponymic nominations, one must consider the multifaceted (intra- and extra-linguistic) principles of allocation of toponymic units, such as: 1) parametric characteristics of an object, 2) ontological characteristics of an object, 3) type of toponymic basis, 4) etymological characteristics of place names, 5) motivational characteristics of place names, 6) chronological characteristics of place names, 7) structural characteristics of toponyms, 8) toponymic polysemy, 9) degree of toponymic nomination, 10) variety of toponymic nomination, 11) localization of an object.

CONCLUSION

To sum up all given ideas, it can be mentioned that toponyms are one of the greatest linguistic and cultural-spiritual wealth of all the countries which was created over the centuries by humanity.

Linguistic toponymy is a specific aspect of toponymy that focuses on the study of place names from a linguistic perspective. It delves into the etymology, structure, and linguistic elements of names given to geographical locations, exploring the connections between language and the names of places.

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